

Open Space Attraction Based Navigation in Dark Tunnels for MAVs^{*}

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Abstract. This work establishes a novel framework for characterizing the open space of featureless dark tunnel environments for Micro Aerial Vehicles (MAVs) navigation tasks. The proposed method leverages the processing of a single camera to identify the deepest area in the scene in order to provide a collision free heading command for the MAV. In the sequel and inspired by haze removal approaches, the proposed novel idea is structured around a single image depth map estimation scheme, without metric depth measurements. The core contribution of the developed framework stems from the extraction of a 2D centroid in the image plane that characterizes the center of the tunnel’s darkest area, which is assumed to represent the open space, while the robustness of the proposed scheme is being examined under varying light/dusty conditions. Simulation and experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method in challenging underground tunnel environments [1].

Keywords: Depth map estimation · Open Space Attraction · Visual Navigation · Micro Aerial Vehicles

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation & Related works

Deploying MAVs in harsh subterranean environments for long term and large scale operations challenge their integrity over time. Lately, the concept of aerial scout robots is emerging in a way to support the operation of the aerial platform that carries the expensive inspection and navigation sensorial units for accomplishing subterranean missions. These platforms are defined as low-cost and lightweight aerial robots that are capable to fly fast in subterranean environments. Their main task is to explore unknown areas, collect data and transmit them back to a ground station.

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Briefly, harsh underground environments pose obstacles for flying MAVs, like the narrow passages, reduced visibility due to rock falls, dust, wind gusts and lack of proper illumination, all of which constitute necessary the development of elaborate control, navigation, and perception modules for these vehicles. This work focuses on a method that will allow MAVs to fly into the darkness of the tunnel, characterizing the open space into a 2D centroid in the image plane. More specifically, inspired by the low illumination challenge, the presented work tries to identify alternative ways for generating a proper guidance command (heading) by using low cost equipment, like a single camera. When flying in underground tunnels, that lack natural illumination, can be really challenging for the visual sensors to provide any useful input. Nevertheless, in this article the main drawback is twisted into the main advantage for the visual sensors, by following the intuition that the darkest area in the image consists of the front looking open space of the tunnel. More specifically, the robot is equipped to carry onboard an illumination source that uniformly illuminates the surrounding walls and ground, while the illumination decreases in longer distances.

Several works in the existing literature have addressed the navigation of MAVs in challenging environments using various sensor configurations. In [8] the fields of estimation, control and mapping for the MAV's autonomous navigation along penstocks, have been studied. In this work the major sensors used were a laser range finder and four cameras for the task of state estimation and mapping. In [10], a range based sensor array approach has been developed to navigate along right-rectangular tunnels and cylindrical shafts. The authors proposed a range sensor configuration, to improve the localization in such environments and provide the means for autonomous navigation. In [7], the authors presented a multi-modal sensor unit for mapping applications, a means for aerial robots to navigate in dark underground tunnels. In this work, the unit consists of a stereo camera, a depth sensor, an IMU and led lights syncs with the camera capture for artificial lightning. Furthermore, the unit has been integrated with a volumetric exploration method, demonstrating the capabilities of the overall system. In [5], a method that fuses visual and depth information with IMU data in an Extended Kalman filter framework has been presented. The proposed system initially extracts keypoints from both the visual and depth sensor using a feature extraction and edge detection method, generating a multi modal feature map. Afterwards, a feature descriptor has been employed and the identified features are fused with the IMU data in the EKF framework.

1.2 Contributions

Nowadays perception algorithms have reached high performance levels in localization and mapping with a major assumption from the scientific and engineering communities that these machines have to operate in environments with adequate features, while the robot motion should be smooth to avoid affecting the outcome of the utilized perception algorithms. It becomes a challenge to accomplish a fully autonomous mission in dark subterranean areas. Thus, in this article, the

proposed novel architecture, approaches the challenges of the tunnel like environment from another point of view, incorporating specific image processing steps, suitable for the navigation purposes. More specifically, this work takes advantage of the area darkness, designing a method that identifies open space in the tunnel by processing single image frame streams. The core concept of the proposed approach is to provide an estimation of the depth-map of the tunnel based on the light scattering method. The depth-map is then further processed to deduce the tunnel free space horizontally and vertically. The process steps include: 1) depth map morphology filtering, 2) region clustering on the filtered depth map, and 3) image binarization and central moment calculation for extracting the area centroid. Secondly, a set of simulation and experimental efforts are presented to demonstrate the performance of the method in challenging environments under varying conditions e.g. illumination, dust and various sensing modalities. The results include: a) a proof-of-concept validation test inside a dark tunnel in a simulated environment, and b) results on dataset from an actual aerial robot, flying in subterranean tunnel using onboard illumination.

1.3 Outline

The rest of the article is structured as it follows. Section 2 describes the overall framework of the proposed centroid extraction method, while Section 3 provides an overview of the simulation results, as well as the results from field datasets, collected from real life experiments with the corresponding analysis and discussion on the results. Finally, Section 4 presents the concluding remarks of the developed system.

2 Methodology

In the proposed approach the characterization of the open space along the tunnel is expressed in the centroid position in the image plane and is based on: a) depth map estimation, b) image binarization, and c) centroid calculation, while Figure 1 depicts the proposed approach.

Fig. 1: An overview of the proposed approach.

2.1 Single Image Depth Estimation

For the proposed depth estimation scheme the starting point is the light scattering [2] method, a well known process where the light is deflected to other

directions and the formation of an image can be defined as follows:

$$I(u, v) = O(u, v) \cdot tr(u, v) + a[1 - tr(u, v)] \quad (1)$$

where $I : [0 \dots M - 1] \times [0 \dots N - 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^2$ is the observed image, $O : [0 \dots M - 1] \times [0 \dots N - 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^2$ is the original image, a is the color of the atmospheric light, $tr(u, v)$ is the transmission term, (u, v) are the pixel coordinates where $u = 0, \dots, M - 1$ and $v = 0, \dots, N - 1$ with M the width and N the height of the image. The first term $O(u, v) \cdot tr(u, v)$ is called direct attenuation [11] and the second term $a[1 - tr(u, v)]$ is called airlight. The transmission term describes the portion of the light that is not scattered and reaches the camera and could be defined as:

$$tr(u, v) = e^{-\beta d(u, v)} \quad (2)$$

where β is the scattering coefficient of the atmosphere and $d(u, v)$ is the depth of the scene for pixel coordinates (u, v) . Although (2) can be utilized for the estimation of a depth map from the original image, for the estimation of the terms $tr(u, v)$ the a is required. A widely used method to extract the transmission map is the DCP method, proposed by [4], in order to estimate the depth map of an image, which can be defined as:

$$tr(u, v) = 1 - \omega \left[\frac{I^{dark}(u, v)}{a} \right], I^{dark}(u, v) = \min_{C \in R, G, B} \left[\min_{z \in \Omega(u, v)} I^C(z) \right] \quad (3)$$

where ω is a number controlling the desired level of restoration with 1 the highest possible value, $I^{dark}(u, v)$ is the dark channel, $\Omega(u, v)$ is a patch of 15×15 pixels centered on (u, v) , I^C is the color channel of the image I and z represents the index of the pixel of $\Omega(u, v)$.

2.2 Open Area Centroid Extraction

Morphological operation & Clustering As mentioned before, $d(u, v)$ represents the depth estimation of the captured scene, without providing metric measurements, but rather a normalized representation. Since in this work metric depth information is not required, a refinement procedure is performed on the $d(u, v)$ to smooth the image using a grey scale morphological operation [9]. More specifically, the algorithm employs a morphological closing $\gamma(d)$ defined in Equation 5, including dilation δ (Equation 4) followed by erosion ϵ (Equation 4) operations with an elliptical structuring element S . The structuring element is passed over the whole image $d(u, v)$ and at each spatial position (u, v) , the relationship between the element and the image is analyzed. For an image I and a structuring element S the erosion and dilation operations are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon(I) &:= I(u, v) \ominus S(u, v) = \min_{\bar{u}, \bar{v} \in S} \{I(u - \bar{u}, v - \bar{v}) - S(u - \bar{u}, v - \bar{v})\} \\ \delta(I) &:= I(u, v) \oplus S(u, v) = \max_{\bar{u}, \bar{v} \in S} \{I(u - \bar{u}, v - \bar{v}) + S(u - \bar{u}, v - \bar{v})\} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \bar{u}, \bar{v} are set by the size of the structuring element. Overall, the morphological closing tries to brighten small, dark areas to match the values of their neighbours in the image, producing the smoothed image $\gamma : [0 \dots M - 1] \times [0 \dots N - 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^2$.

$$\gamma(d) = \epsilon(\delta(d)) \quad (5)$$

Afterwards γ is processed through a segmentation method to divide into a discrete number of regions that include pixels with high similarities. In the proposed approach, the computationally efficient k -means [12] clustering algorithm is employed in order to segment the depth image into a predefined number of clusters $C = \{k_i\}$, where $k_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denote the cluster centers and $i = 1, \dots, 10$. Initially, the algorithm assigns random k_i for each cluster. Then the euclidean distance of each point $\gamma(u_M, v_N)$ in the image with every k_i is computed as shown in Equation 6.

$$\text{dist}(k_i, \gamma(u_M, v_N)) = \sqrt{(\gamma(u_M) - k_{i,u})^2 + (\gamma(v_N) - k_{i,v})^2} \quad (6)$$

Afterwards all image points are assigned to the respective cluster based in Equation 7.

$$\arg \min_{C_i \in C} \text{dist}(k_i, \gamma(u_M, v_N))^2 \quad (7)$$

Then, the cluster centroids are calculated again, based on average of all points that currently belong to the cluster and the process is repeated until convergence based on termination criteria. The overall process leads to the clustered image $d_{clustered} : [0 \dots M - 1] \times [0 \dots N - 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^2$.

In the sequel, $d_{clustered}$ is further processed to provide a binary image d_{binary} that isolates the dark area from the rest of the image surroundings. More specifically, the cluster center k_i with the minimum image intensity is extracted and the pixels intensities are set to 1, while the rest pixels are set to 0.

Centroid Finally, the centroid (s_x, s_y) of the binarized depth image $d_{binary}(u, v)$ is extracted using the image moments [3]. More specifically, the geometric moments M_{pq} of $d_{binary}(u, v)$ are defined using a discrete sum approximation as shown in Equation 8, while (s_x, s_y) are calculated according to Equation 9.

$$M_{pq} = \sum_u \sum_v u^p v^q d_{binary}(u, v) \quad (8)$$

$$s_x = \frac{M_{10}}{M_{00}}, \quad s_y = \frac{M_{01}}{M_{00}} \quad (9)$$

where M_{00} represents the area in the binary image, M_{10} is the sum over x and M_{01} is the sum over y . The normalized pixel coordinates s_x and $s_y \in \mathbb{R}$ can be defined as:

$$s_x = (u - o_x)/f_x, \quad s_y = (v - o_y)/f_y, \quad (10)$$

where $o_x \in \mathbb{N}$ and $o_y \in \mathbb{N}$ are the principal points in pixels, $f_x, f_y \in \mathbb{R}$ are the camera focal length for the pixel columns and rows respectively.

The calculated centroid is visualized with a red circle in the sequential frames, while the visual processing architecture provides the centroid with update rates of 20 Hz. Figure 2 depicts an example of the extracted centroid overlaid in the onboard captured image as well as the generated single image depth map.

Fig. 2: On the left onboard image frame with the extracted centroid denoted with the red circle, while on the right the estimated depth map from a single image is depicted.

3 Results

This section reports results both from simulation and experimental trials using the proposed method. More specifically, the simulation results present the overall navigation concept depicting the guidance of a MAV along a dark tunnel, while the experimental results focus on the performance analysis of the centroid extraction from collected datasets. Moreover, the code is written in C++ within Robot Operating System¹ (ROS) framework.

3.1 Simulation Results

The proposed framework has been initially evaluated in the Gazebo [6] robot simulation environment interfaced to ROS. The simulated quadrotor is equipped with a front-facing camera, while this simulation demonstrates the envisioned application of the tunnel open area extraction method, described in Section 2. The centroid extraction method is part of the overall navigation stack, which also includes state estimation and control that are considered black boxes. In a nutshell, the s_x , s_y are one part of the inputs to the controller, which is assigned to provides the motor commands for the quadrotor to navigate along the tunnel. In this simulation, the gazebo world ² “*tunnel_practice_2.world*”, developed for the DARPA Subterranean challenge³, has been selected for deploying the aerial platform.

¹ <http://www.ros.org/>

² <https://bitbucket.org/osrf/subt/wiki/Home>

³ <https://subtchallenge.com/>

Fig. 3: On the left ground truth 3D performed translation of the MAV during the navigation in the simulated tunnel, on the right centroid s_x evolution over time during the navigation in the simulated tunnel. The following video demonstrates the simulation results <https://youtu.be/x5T72ndiMxc>.

Figure 3 depicts the total ground truth path that the MAV followed. Additionally, this Figure showcases the evolution of the normalized s_x over time. For the first 20 sec, the aerial platform starts from an off-center pose outside the tunnel and therefore the centroid on the x axis is slightly oscillating in a way that guides the MAV inside the tunnel. For the time instances 38 sec, 65 sec, 140 sec, 150 sec and 165 sec the centroid reaches peak values, depicting that the tunnel is taking a turn and the MAV has to yaw along the axis.

3.2 Experimental Results

Dataset Acquisition and Description In this section, the proposed novel method is evaluated using datasets collected from real autonomous experiments in an underground mine located in Sweden at 790 m deep, where the underground tunnels did not have strong corrupting magnetic fields, their morphology resembled an S shape environment with small inclination. The dimensions of the area where the MAV navigates autonomously were 6(width) \times 4(height) \times 20(length)m³. The dataset has been collected from an PlayStation Eye camera, mounted onboard the aerial vehicle, operated at 30 fps and with a resolution of 640 \times 480 pixels, a 2D Lidar, while the LED light bars provided 460 lux illumination in 1 m distance. The MAV was flying at 1 m altitude relative to the ground, moving forward with a constant velocity $v_{d,x}$ of 0.2 m/s. Figure 1 provides a visualization of different parts of the underground tunnel.

Performance analysis This Section presents the application of the proposed method on the collected datasets, focusing on the performance in real environments, as well as the challenges, such as different illumination conditions and also dust that the algorithm come across. Figure 4 depicts snapshots with the extracted s_x , s_y for different time instances, where on the bottom part provides an overall visualization of the direction commands at various time instances over the traversed course. More specifically, using the data from the onboard 2D lidar, a 2D occupancy grid map is generated, showing the area covered in the tunnel.

Fig. 4: a) - c) depict onboard image frames with the extracted centroid denoted with the red circle, d) depicts the direction commands with green arrow, the current pose with red arrow both overlaid on a 2D occupancy grid map. The following video demonstrates results <https://youtu.be/x5T72ndiMxc> from a real subterranean environment.

The map has been augmented with red and green arrows that show the current pose and the instant direction command respectively. The map and the red arrows are part of the collected dataset and cannot be modified, while the green arrows are the result of the proposed centroid extraction method. This figure is representative of the overall performance of the method and can be divided into three parts: 1) the straight tunnel path, 2) the curve, and 3) the open areas. For the straight tunnel path, the majority of the direction commands tend to orient the aerial robot closer to the tunnel axis. For the curve part of the tunnel the centroid is affected by the combination of curve geometry and the illumination. Figure 4a) demonstrates that there could be cases where the curve is visible long before reaching it and therefore the direction command will lean towards it, which in the sequel will drive the MAV closer to the wall. Overall, this is mostly the case for wide tunnels and the navigation is not majorly affected. The third part of the map shows an open space, where in this situation the proposed algorithm will drive the MAV to the area that is less illuminated.

Applying the proposed method on datasets from real underground tunnels, apart from providing an insight on performance, it also brings up challenges that should be addressed. More specifically, Figure 5 showcases various occasions where the performance is affected due to harsh conditions. The starting point is the tunnel geometry where the tunnel width forms a critical factor. The algorithm showed to be able to perform equally well in both narrow and wide tunnels and in areas where the tunnels lack any natural illumination (Figure 5d). Moreover, the developed method is partly able to address the dust floating in

the tunnel, while flying (Figure 5b). The final point of discussion focuses on areas where an additional illumination source exists apart from the onboard, distorting the estimated depth images and overall the guidance command. For wide tunnels the additional illumination source affects slightly the commands when the MAV is flying closely (Figure 5a), while in narrow tunnels the illumination source affects majorly the guidance command, where in some cases the centroid is pointed in darker areas (e.g. the wall) away from the tunnel open space (Figure 5c). In a summary, the proposed method has been developed to address the guidance command generation for completely dark areas, assuming that the aerial robot has an onboard illumination source, providing substantial performance characteristics.

Fig. 5: Challenging test cases including: a) varying illumination in a wide tunnel, b) dust in a wide tunnel, c) varying illumination in a narrow tunnel, and d) narrow tunnel general case. All cases depict the onboard image with the depth map.

Finally, the centroid method has been tested in image frames collected from an underground tunnel environment with extremely low illumination of 40lux. The method seems that is able to handle the low illumination levels and provides the estimated depth map from a real dark image, as depicted in Figure 6. Future directions will focus on a generalized characterization method that will address the problem in cases where dust and varying illumination sources are evident in the scene.

Fig. 6: Centroid extraction method in dark images

4 Conclusions

This work proposed a framework for characterizing open space in featureless dark tunnel-like environments using information from the image stream from a single onboard camera. The proposed method leverages the processing of a single camera to identify the area in the scene with the largest depth value, which is expressed through a 2D centroid in the image plane, without using metric depth measurements. The proposed method has been developed to address the guidance command generation for completely dark areas, providing substantial performance characteristics. Future directions will focus on a generalized characterization method that will address the problem in cases where dust and varying illumination sources are evident in the scene.

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